

Critical thinking about treatments test

Side 1

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

Invitation to take part in the Critical thinking of treatments questionnaire

The Informed Health Choices project on critical thinking about health claims and choices is a research collaboration including universities in Kenya, Rwanda, Uganda and Norway. The overall goal is to improve people's health by helping the public to appraise health information.

You have been identified as one of the key persons that can participate in this study and we are therefore seeking permission for you to participate in this study. Below you will find a questionnaire that assesses critical thinking.

Your participation in the study will help us improve the resources we develop as part of the Informed Health Choices project.

There will be no direct benefit to you from participating in this study and there is no promise of gaining any material or financial benefit from the project currently or in the future. You will incur a minimal cost of data bundles as a result of taking part in the study and may not gain any form of compensation, monetary or otherwise for participating in the study.

Your views are important to us and we hope that you will take the time to participate in this study.

To participate, please continue to the next page and provide your responses to the best of your ability. Answering this questionnaire will take between 20- 40 minutes. If you want, you can take a pause while responding to the questionnaire, but please make sure that you do not leave the website. If you leave the website without completing the questionnaire, your responses will not be saved.

In case of any further questions, please contact your country contact person:

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Sideskift

Side 2

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

Before you start, please note that some words in this questionnaire may not be familiar to you. Please read through the following explanations:

A TREATMENT is anything done to care for yourself, so you stay well or, if you are sick or injured, so you get better and not worse. For example, skin cream.

A TREATMENT CLAIM is something someone says about whether a treatment causes something to happen or to change. A claim can be true or can be false. For example, using skin cream for skin rash.

A RESEARCH STUDY is a way to answer a question by carefully collecting information. For example, a study might be done to answer the question: Does skin cream help people with skin rash?

RESULTS of a study are what the study found. For example, whether people who use skin cream had less skin rash.

When something happens by **CHANCE**, it is not possible to tell in advance what will happen. For example, if you flip a coin, you cannot tell in advance if it will land on one side or the other side.

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

Part 1. Questions about you

1. What is your gender? *

Female

Male

2. How old are you? *

Between 10 and 18

19 or older

3. What is your level of education completed? *

No education

Primary education

Secondary education

Tertiary education/ university

4. Have you ever been a research participant in scientific research? *

Yes

No

Don't know

5. Have you any training in scientific research (statistics, epidemiology, randomised controlled trials)? *

Yes

No

Don't know

6. What country are you living in? *

Kenya

Uganda

Rwanda

Sideskift

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Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

Part 2. Questions about claims

1. Mary wanted to find out which plants were best for treating people with headaches, so she did a research study to compare green plants with yellow plants. The people who used the green plants had fewer headaches compared to the people who used the yellow plants. *

Question: How sure can we be that green plants are better than yellow plants?

It is not possible to say. Mary did not study possible harms of the plants

Very sure, since people who used the green plants had fewer headaches

Not very sure, it depends on how much people believe the green plants will work

Sideskift

Side 5

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

2. Regina has a sickness that makes it difficult for her to breathe. She hears on the radio about a medicine that has helped many people with breathing problems. *

Question: How sure can Regina be that the medicine does not have any harms?

- It is not possible to say, it depends on how much hope Regina has in the medicine
- Very sure, since the medicine has helped many people, it is unlikely that it also harms people
- Not very sure, because all medicines may harm people as well as help them

Side 6

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

3. Mr Mukasa is very sick. The doctors say that there is no cure for his sickness, but he still hopes there is something that can help him. He hears about a new medicine that other people with his sickness have used. *

Question: Mr Mukasa has four family members giving him advice. What is the best advice?

- His brother says the medicine will help if Mr Mukasa hopes it will
- His daughter says trying out the new medicine cannot do any harm since Mr Mukasa is very sick
- His wife says it is not possible to say if the medicine will help him, because it may also have harmful effects

Side 7

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

4. Gladys uses a new soap for her pimples (spots). Since she started using the new soap, her pimples have gone away. Her neighbour has many pimples. Gladys believes the new soap will help, and tells her neighbour to use it. *

Question: Do you agree with what Gladys believes?

- It is not possible to say, without knowing how similar Gladys' skin is to her neighbour's skin
- Yes, if the new soap worked for Gladys, it should work for other people's pimples
- No, because Gladys' experience is not enough to know whether the new soap makes pimples go away

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Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

5. Imagine you have a fever and a new treatment for fever is available in the shops. *

Question: Is the new treatment much more likely to be better than older treatments?

- Yes, new treatments are always tested and proved to be better than older treatments before they are made available in the shops
- No, new treatments are only slightly more likely to be better than older treatments, and they may be harmful
- No, old treatments are much more likely to be better, because many people have tried them

Side 9

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

6. Sarah says that medicines from well-known companies, costing more money, are not necessarily the best. Medicines from less known companies, costing less money, may be just as good or even better. *

Question: Is Sarah right?

- No, medicines costing less money are more likely to be harmful than expensive medicines
- Yes, just because the medicine is expensive does not mean that it will work better than other medicines
- No, expensive medicines made by well-known companies are better than less expensive medicines made by lesser-known companies

Side 10

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

7. A doctor did a study comparing a new medicine to an old medicine in 2000 people with heart disease. The doctor flipped a coin and divided people into two groups. One group got the new medicine and the other group got the old medicine. He found that two people who took the old medicine died, and four people who took the new medicine died. *

Question: Which of the following statements is correct?

- The number of deaths was too small to be sure that the old medicine is better or worse than the new medicine
- We can be sure that the old medicine is better than the new medicine, because half as many people who took it died
- We can be sure that the old medicine is better than the new medicine because the study included 2000 people

Side 11

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

8. A doctor wanted to know which of two treatments was best for headaches. In a study to find out, he asked people to choose which treatment they would like to get. He compared the people who took each of the two treatments. *

Question: How sure can we be about the results of this comparison of the two treatments?

- More sure, because the doctor asked people to choose which treatment they wanted
- Less sure, because the doctor should have decided who got which treatment
- Less sure, because the doctor should have given people one of the two treatments by chance (like flipping a coin)

Side 12

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

9. Jane often has headaches. Her doctor tells her that there is a medicine that may help her, but it may harm her. The medicine is also very expensive. *

Question: What does Jane need to think about before using the medicine?

- If the medicine will help her more than it will hurt her, and if she thinks it is worth paying so much money for it
- If anybody she knows has tried the medicine so that she can ask them what they thought about it
- If she should ask another doctor, since the doctor must be wrong. A medicine which is helpful cannot be harmful

Side 13

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

10. John has a skin rash on his leg. A shop sells several skin creams to treat skin rashes. John chooses a skin cream from a well-known company, even though it is more expensive than the other creams. John thinks this skin cream is more likely to heal his rash than the other skin creams because it is more expensive.

Question: Is John right?

- No, just because the skin cream is expensive does not mean that it will work better than other creams
- It is not possible to say. However, expensive skin creams are likely to be better because the companies spend more time making them
- No, the skin cream is probably not as good as the other skin creams. People just like well-known companies more

Side 14

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

11. George has stomach pain. The last time George had a stomach pain was two months ago. That time, he drank some hot milk and after an hour, his stomach pain was gone. Therefore, George says hot milk cures stomach pain. *

Question: Is George right?

- It is not possible to say. His stomach pain might have gone away without the hot milk
- It is not possible to say, but it is likely to be true based on the fact that George had this experience
- Yes, George's experience is enough to show that hot milk makes stomach pain go away

Side 15

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

12. Anne has pain in her ear, and she asks her brother Hassan what to do about it. He says that once, when he had a pain like that, he cleaned his ear with hot water. The next day, his ear pain was gone. Based on his experience, he says rinsing with hot water is helpful for ear pain. *

Question: Do you agree with Hassan?

- Yes. Because this is Hassan's experience, it is likely to be true
- No, Hassan's experience is not enough to be sure
- Yes, Hassan rinsed his ear with hot water and the next day his ear pain was gone

Side 16

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

13. Imagine you hear about a drink made from oranges on the radio. The makers of the drink say that if you have some of it every day, you will live a long life. *

Question: Based on this, how sure can you be that oranges will give you a long life?

- Very sure, because the drink probably tastes good
- Not very sure. Very few treatments help everyone who takes them
- Very sure. If it was not true, the makers of the drink would not have said this

Side 17

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

14. Esther recommends a new treatment – a medicine - for pain. She says that everyone who has tried it felt better. *

Question: How sure can you be that what Esther says about the new medicine is true?

- Not very sure. Very large benefits, where everyone or nearly everyone gets better because of a treatment are rare
- It is not possible to say. To be sure I would have to try the medicine for myself
- Very sure. The medicine must be very good since everyone who has tried it got better

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

15. On the radio, there is someone selling a treatment - a new juice. The seller says that if you drink one glass of it every day, you will not get sick. *

Question: How sure can you be that the new juice will keep you from getting sick?

- It is not possible to say. I would have to try the new juice myself to be sure
- Very sure, otherwise this news would not be on the radio
- Not very sure. Very few treatments work so well

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

16. Imagine you read a story in the newspaper about a plant medicine for treating headaches. In the story, a doctor says that even though the medicine has been used for a long time and that many people say it has worked for them, we cannot be very sure that it is helpful. *

Question: The doctor is right, but why do you think he is?

- He is a doctor, and we can trust what he says
- The people who have tried the plant medicine may not be telling the truth
- The plant medicine may not have been compared to other treatments in studies

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

17. Edith has stomach pain. Edith's mother says that fruit juice is a good treatment for stomach pain. She learnt about this treatment from Edith's grandmother. Over many years, other families she knows have also used fruit juice to treat stomach pain. *

Question: Based on this, how sure can we be that fruit juice is a good treatment for stomach pain?

- Not very sure. Even though people have used fruit juice over many years, that does not mean that it helps stomach pain
- Very sure. If it has worked for Edith's mother and other people who have tried it, it will probably work for her too
- Not very sure. Edith should ask more families if they use fruit juice to treat stomach pain

 Sideskift

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Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

18. Outside the city where Paul lives there are many farms. The farmers often get coughs. For many years, the farmers have used strong tea to treat their coughs. They say that the tea is good for them and that it protects them from becoming more sick. Paul says that the farmers may not be right, and that the strong tea may not help coughs.

Question: Do you agree with Paul?

- Yes, Paul should try drinking strong tea himself to know for sure. The strong tea may work differently on him
- Yes, we can only know for sure if the strong tea works if it has been compared with other treatments in studies
- No, the farmers would not have used strong tea for all those years if it did not work

 Sideskift

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Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

19. Doctors studied people with stomach pain before and after they took a new medicine. After taking the new medicine, many people felt less pain. *

Question: Can we be sure that the new medicine is good for treating stomach pain?

- No, taking the new medicine should have been compared either with not taking the medicine, or with taking an older medicine
- Yes, people were asked how much pain they felt before and after they took the new medicine
- Yes, the study was done by doctors

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Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

20. Dr. Javier has done a research study giving a new medicine to people who were vomiting. Some of the people stopped vomiting after they got the new medicine. Dr. Javier says that this means that the medicine works. *

Question: Is Dr. Javier right?

- No. The people who used the medicine were not compared with similar people who did not use the medicine
- Yes, some of the people stopped vomiting
- No, since not all the people stopped vomiting

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Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

21. Shakira has heard that eating mangos makes you feel better. She decides to find out if this is true. For one week, she made her friends eat mangos every day. At the end of the week, most of her friends said they felt better. *

Question: Can Shakira be sure that eating mangos makes you feel better?

- No, not all of Shakira's friends felt better after eating mangos every day
- Yes, she treated all her friends equally by making them all eat mangos
- No, Shakira's friends were not compared to similar people who did not eat mangos

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

22. A new and an old mosquito spray (insecticide) were compared in a research study. In the study, two houses were sprayed with the new spray, and two houses were sprayed with the old spray. Based on this study, the new spray was better for protecting against mosquito bites than the old spray. Neither of the sprays was found to be harmful to people. *

Question: How sure can you be about what the study found?

- Less sure, because only four houses were studied and the differences between sprays may have happened by chance
- More sure, because the new spray was better for protecting against mosquito bites and it was not harmful
- More sure, because the new spray was found to be better, and the differences between sprays is unlikely to have happened by chance

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

23. Mercy wanted to know if eating bananas makes you run faster. To find out, she invited her six best friends to take part in a research study. Three friends each got bananas, and three friends did not get bananas. At the end of the study, the friends who did not get bananas ran a lot faster. *

Question: How sure can Mercy be about her study's results?

- More sure, because Mercy found a difference between the groups in how fast they ran. This means that the study included enough people.
- Less sure, because the difference between the two groups could have occurred by chance
- More sure, if she repeats the study with six more friends

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

24. In a research study, doctors gave a new treatment - a medicine - to people with stomach pain, and an older medicine to similar people. The doctors decided who should get the old treatment and the new treatment. *

Question: How sure can we be about the results of this comparison of the two treatments?

- Less sure, because people should have been able to decide which treatment they were given
- Less sure, because chance (like flipping a coin) should have been used to decide which of the two treatments each patient would receive
- Less sure, because both groups should have got the new treatment

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Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

25. Imagine you and your friends have formed a team to take part in a local running competition. People on the other teams all had bananas for breakfast. You and your friends did not have bananas for breakfast and lost the race. Some people say that this was because your team had bread for breakfast and that made them run slower. *

Question: If you did a research study comparing people who eat bananas for breakfast with people who don't eat bananas for breakfast, how would you decide who should have bananas for breakfast?

- By chance (like flipping a coin) to make sure the two groups are as similar as possible
- By having the teams decide, to make it as fair as possible
- By having the teachers decide, because they know who would benefit best from eating bananas

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Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

26. Sarah has a sickness. There is a medicine for it, but she is not sure if she should try it. A research study comparing the medicine with no medicine found that the medicine was helpful but also that it could be harmful. Three of Sarah's friends are telling her what to do. *

Question: Which of the following things said by her friends is more correct?

- She should only take the medicine if many people have tried the medicine before
- She should only take the medicine if she thinks it will help her more than it will harm her
- If Sarah has enough money to buy the medicine, it could not hurt to try it

Side 30

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

27. John is sick. There is a new medicine available for his sickness. However, his doctor says that taking the medicine may not be the best for John. *

Question: What is the best reason for this?

- The medicine may be more harmful than it is helpful, and not worth the costs
- The medicine may be harmful, and unlikely to be helpful
- The medicine may cost a lot of money, but if John can pay for it, he should take it

Part 3. Questions about your views

Think about a sickness that you might get. Imagine someone claiming (saying) that a treatment might help you get better. Below are some questions about what you think. There are not right or wrong answers to these questions.

*

28. Question: How likely are you to find out what the claim was based on (for example by asking the person making the claim)?

- Very unlikely
- Unlikely
- Likely
- Very likely
- I don't know

*

29. Question: How likely are you to find out if the claim was based on a research study comparing the treatment to no treatment?

 Very unlikely Unlikely Likely Very likely I don't know

*

30. Question: How likely are you to say “yes” if you are asked to participate in a research study comparing two treatments for your sickness?

 Very unlikely Unlikely Likely Very likely I don't know

Sideskift

Side 31

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

Below are some actions. Please read each one carefully and give the answer that comes closest to how difficult or easy you find each of the actions to be. There are not right or wrong answers to these questions.

*

31. Question: How difficult or easy do you find knowing if a claim about a treatment is based on a research study comparing treatments?

 Very difficult Difficult Easy Very easy I don't know

*

32. Question: How difficult or easy do you think it is to find information about treatments that is based on research studies comparing treatments?

Very difficult

Difficult

Easy

Very easy

I don't know

*

33. Question: How difficult or easy do you find knowing how to be sure about the results of a research study comparing treatments?

Very difficult

Difficult

Easy

Very easy

I don't know

*

34. Question: How difficult or easy do you find knowing if the results of a research study comparing treatments are relevant to you?

Very difficult

Difficult

Easy

Very easy

I don't know

Obligatoriske felter er merket med denne stjernen *

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